

AN INTRODUCTION OF AN ELEMENT OF INTERPHASE IN MODELING FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the effect of the interphase between the fiber and the matrix is numerically studied for tensile and transverse loading of an hexagonal-array unidirectional monofiber. This interphase consists of an entity of a significant thickness. It was assumed that the mechanical properties of the interphase unfold from those of the fiber to those of the matrix. The Representative Volume Element (RVE) composed of three phases is modeled by three dimensional isoparametric hexahedral elements and two other brick elements. In the interphase finite element the elasticity matrix was integrated in the Gauss points. To study the effect of interphase thickness, stress and strain states have been analyzed for different values of the fiber volume fraction so for various interphase thickness. The results for a fiber epoxy were compared with the cases of a perfect interface.

INTRODUCTION

It is widely recognized that the adhesion between matrix and inclusions (fiber or particulates) in a composite material is one of the principal factors characterizing the mechanical and physical behavior as well as stiffness and strength of the modern composite materials under many different load cases.

In fact, all the existing numerical models describing do not take into account the influence of the boundary layer developed between phases. In the literature, this adhesion has been modeled either perfect interface with an infinite stiffness, which means that displacements are continuous across the interface or a poor interface with a zero stiffness.

The effect of an interphase on a composite's mechanical and thermal behavior has been investigated by a number of authors. Theocaris et al. (1985), Sideridis (1988), Benveniste et al. (1989) and Dasgupta A. and Bhandarkhar S.M. (1992) have described the interphase as a layer between inclusions and matrix. This interphase has a significant thickness and elastic properties which differ from those of the matrix and the fiber. M.R. Piggot (1990) has measured the interphase/interface properties by using simple fiber pull out tests.

On the other hand, the spring model has been discussed by Lene and Leguillon (1982), Benveniste (1987), Aboudi (1990), Achenbach and Zhu (1990) and Hashin (1990).

The effect of interphase stiffness on a micromechanical and macromechanical behaviors has been investigated for transverse loading of an hexagonal-array unidirectional fiber composite by Achenbach and Zhu.

In the present work, the interface is considered as an entity called interphase with its own mechanical properties, based on the Theocaris et al. model. In this order the volumetric representative element used in this investigation is composed of three phases: fiber, matrix and interphase. In this latter the elastic modulus value decreases from the high value of the fiber elastic modulus to that of the matrix as a power function of a specific exponent. A parabolic function of the Poisson's ratio is assumed into the interphase thickness radius.

A fiber glass epoxy is modeled by a three-dimensional isoparametric hexahedral element and two other brick elements. So, an interphase finite element is established with the introduction of the brick element of the elastic modulus expression integrated at the Gauss points. The results of this analysis give the micromechanical fields of stress and deformation in any layer.

THE VOLUMIC REPRESENTATIF ELEMENT

Fig.1: Schematic representation of the model wed for the RVE of a unidirectional fiber composite

The RVE of a fiber reinforced composite is presented in Fig.1. It is composed of three phases: fiber, interphase and matrix with a significant thickness. The volume fractions of the phase are given by:

$$V_f = \frac{2\Pi}{3\sqrt{3}} \frac{r_f^2}{d_m^2} \quad V_i = \frac{2\Pi}{3\sqrt{3}} \frac{r_i^2 - r_f^2}{d_m^2} \quad V_m = 1 - \frac{2\Pi}{3\sqrt{3}} \frac{r_i^2}{d_m^2} \quad (1)$$

where r_f, r_i are fiber and matrix radii respectively
 d_m is the distance of the matrix corner to the fiber center.

We assume that the interphase is an inhomogeneous material of finite thickness where we can define a variable elastic modulus $E_i(r)$ and shear modulus and shear modulus $G_i(r)$ depending only on the polar distance. In other words, we assume that the interphase layer consists of a series of elementary layers whose constant mechanical properties differ from others by a quantity defined by the law of variation of $E_i(r)$ and $G_i(r)$.

To smooth out the large differences between the moduli of the fiber and the matrix in a very thin layers of the interphase, it is shown [2] that the appropriate functions for $E_i(r)$ are power function with large negative exponents.

Let the expression of $E_i(r)$ for $r \in [r_f, r_i]$

$$E_i(r) = E_f \left(\frac{r_f}{r}\right)^{2\eta} + [E_m - E_f \left(\frac{r_f}{r_i}\right)^{2\eta}] \frac{(r - r_f)}{(r_i - r_f)} \quad (2)$$

Where E_f, E_m are the fiber and matrix longitudinal modulus respectively.

The relation satisfied the boundary conditions:

At $r = r_f$ we have $E_i(r) = E_f$

At $r = r_i$ $E_i(r) = E_m$

We assume a parabolic variation of $G_i(r)$ given by :

$$G_i(r) = A r^2 + B r + C \quad \text{for } r \in [r_f, r_i] \quad (3)$$

In order to evaluation A,B,C we take into consideration the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{At } r = r_f & \quad G_i(r) = G_f \\ r = r_i & \quad G_i(r) = G_m \\ r = r_i & \quad \frac{dG_i(r)}{dr} = \text{with } \frac{d^2G_i(r)}{dr^2} > 0 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting there volume we obtain:

$$G_i(r) = \frac{G_f - G_m}{(r_i - r_f)^2} r^2 - \frac{(G_f - G_m) r_i}{(r_i - r_f)^2} r + \frac{G_f r_i^2 + G_m r_f^2 - 2G_m r_f r_i}{(r_i - r_f)^2} \quad (4)$$

where G_f , G_m are fiber and matrix shear moduli respectively.

INTERPHASE THICKNESS

To evaluate the interphase thickness, the epoxy and the glass epoxy are taken into a differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and we effect measurements of discontinuous changes in heat capacity at the glass-transition temperature T_g .

It has been observed that for the same volume fraction of the glass fiber, an increase of T_g indicates an increasing of the total surface of the fiber [2]. This is equivalent to an increase in the proportion of macromolecules participating in this boundary layers with reduced mobilities, so that the number of macromolecules participating in the T_g process is reduced. This yields to an increasing of v_i .

Lipatov indicated that there is a relation between a weight constant λ , defining the interphase volume fraction V_i , and the jumps of the heat capacity ΔC_p^f of the filled composite and ΔC_p^0 of the unfilled polymer

$$\frac{(r_f + \Delta r_i)^2}{r_f^2} - 1 = \frac{\lambda V_f}{1 - V_f} \quad (5)$$

Where λ is a real constant :

$$\lambda = 1 - \frac{\Delta C_p^f}{\Delta C_p^0} \quad (6)$$

For the glass fiber epoxy, theocariss has found the values of the thickness interphase and the exponent η for various values of fiber contents

V_f %	V_i %	V_m %	Δr_i μm	η μm	r_i μm	r_m^* μm	r_m^{**} μm
20	0.492	79.508	0.073	110	10.073	24.464	24.5880
40	1.960	58.040	0.146	57	10.146	17.215	17.3868
60	4.428	35.572	0.217	39	10.217	14.000	14.1960
80	7.900	12.100	0.288	29	10.288	12.067	12.2943

* Case of the composite with an interphase,

** Case of the composite with a perfect interface.

With : $\Delta r_i = r_i - r_f$

THREE DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS

The continuous fiber composite is simulated by an hexagonal-array infinitely long volum, as shown in figure 1. This VER contains two concentric circular cylinders. A cartesian coordinates system (x,y,z) is assumed. The x-axis is in the fiber direction.

The two cylinders representing fiber and interphase are including in hexagonal-array volum matrix. Three ditional prismatic and hexaedric isoparametric finite element are used in the VER mesh. In the interphase finite element formulation, the elastic matrix is not constant in the numerical integration.

The isoparametric formulation extends directly from two dimensions to three. Once the displacement distributions are specified, the formulation of the solid finite element stiffness is straightforward. The strain-displacement relationship for these element is expressed as:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u}_n \quad (7)$$

where

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \rangle = \langle u_{,x} \quad v_{,y} \quad w_{,z} \quad u_{,y}+v_{,x} \quad u_{,z}+w_{,x} \quad v_{,z}+w_{,y} \rangle \quad (8)$$

$$\langle \mathbf{u}_n \rangle = \langle u_1 \quad v_1 \quad w_1 \quad \dots \quad u_n \quad v_n \quad w_n \rangle$$

n=6 for a prismatic element with 6 nodes
n=8 for a hexaedric element with 8 nodes.

The strain-displacement operator **B** in equation (7) has the form:

$$\mathbf{B} = \left[\begin{array}{c|ccc} & B_{1j} & 0 & 0 \\ & 0 & B_{2i} & 0 \\ \dots & 0 & 0 & B_{3i} \\ & B_{2i} & B_{1i} & 0 \\ & B_{3i} & 0 & B_{1i} \\ & 0 & B_{3i} & B_{2i} \end{array} \right] \quad i=1,n \quad (9)$$

The operator **B** components are given by :

$$\begin{bmatrix} B_{1i} \\ B_{2i} \\ B_{3i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} J_{11} & J_{12} & J_{13} \\ J_{21} & J_{22} & J_{23} \\ J_{31} & J_{32} & J_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} N_{i,\xi} \\ N_{i,\eta} \\ N_{i,\zeta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x,\xi & y,\xi & z,\xi \\ x,\eta & y,\eta & z,\eta \\ x,\zeta & y,\zeta & z,\zeta \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} N_{i,\xi} \\ N_{i,\eta} \\ N_{i,\zeta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Where (ξ, η, ζ) are a natural or intrinsec coordinates

J jacobian matrix
N Shape functions

Integration of the virtual work equations yields the stiffness equations for the element (Zienkiewicz [11]).

Finally, the stiffness matrix is:

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{-1}^{+1} \int_{-1}^{+1} \int_{-1}^{+1} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{E} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{J} \, d\xi \, d\eta \, d\zeta \quad (11)$$

For the interphase element, $[E]$ is not constant.

Then $E = E_i(r)$

$$v = v_i(r)$$

r is the distance of the Gauss point's to the fiber axe.

In this case (ox is the fiber axis) :

$$r = \sqrt{(y_G - y_0)^2 + (z_G - z_0)^2}$$

(x_G, y_G, z_G) are the gauss points coordinates.

(x_0, y_0, z_0) are the polar distance

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The glass-fiber composites used in the present investigation consisted of an epoxy matrix reinforced with long E-glass fibers. The fiber diameter value is $10 \mu\text{m}$.

The mechanical properties of matrix and fiber are:

$$E_m = 4500 \text{ MPa} \quad v_m = 0,4$$

$$E_f = 73000 \text{ MPa} \quad v_f = 0,25$$

Three different fiber volume fractions (V_f)-0.2,0.4 and 0.6 are considered .

Under a uniform axial-pressure $P=120 \text{ MPa}$ on plan (Y,Z) , the axial and Y stresses along the Y direction for $V_f=0.2$ are shown in Fig.2 and 3 .

The same behavior has been seen for $V_f=0.4$ and 0.6 . It is shown that continus variations in the interphase elastic moduli assure the continuity of stress in the interphase. We can also see from these results that the axial stress in the perfect interface is smaller than that of the interphase model

Fig.2: Axial stress distribution along the Y distance for a tensile load (120 MPa , $V_f=0.2$)

Fig.3: Y-stress σ_y distribution along the Y distance for a tensile load (120 MPa , $V_f=0.2$).

The monofiler is subjected to a uniform transverse pressure $P=100$ MPa in the external side. The distributions of stresses σ_x, σ_y along the Y distance are plotted in fig.4 and 5. It is shown that the fiber is compressed in the same way for the two cases. The differences is situated in the interphase element. Figure 4 shown that the compression is extended in the interphase element. The maximum stress occurs in the interface fibre/interphase.

Fig.4: Axial-stress distribution along the Y-distance for a transverse load (100MPa, $V_f=0.2$).

Fig.5 : Z-stress distribution along the Z-distance for a transverse load (100MPa, $V_f=0.2$).

CONCLUSION

Currently, the chemical characterization of the fiber/matrix interphase is receiving a great deal of attention. Experimentally, the constitutive variable properties of the interphase can be detected. This interphase is modeled by using degraded properties for the main phases.

A three dimentional finite element is developed to simulate variation in the interphase elastic moduli. A power and parabolic function of the polar distance from the fiber was assumed for the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio respectively. To determine stiffness matrix in interphase finite element, the elastic matrix is integrated of the point's gauss.

A finite dement analysis is carried out to demonstrate how the interphase thickness, the fiber volum fraction and the elastic modulus function's affect the local stress state. Results are compared to those of perfect interface case.

In this first study, the conditions of loading applied by pressure on plan (Y,Z) or on hexagon's face along the X axe, appeared very penalizing for transverse behaviour interfaces.

By used of asymptotic homogeneization schemes, this model could readily be extended to describe the impregnated composite's behavior. To further work, the effect of the interphase element in the global elastic moduli could be analysed.

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